

THE NIGERIAN FUEL ENERGY SUPPLY CRISIS AND THE PROPOSED PRIVATE REFINERIES – PROSPECTS AND PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

Dynamism of the world economy has compelled Nigerians to accept the liberalization of its economy to encourage private sector participation and induce managerial efficiency. This has become very imperative most especially, in the downstream sub-sector of the Nigerian oil and gas industry by the establishment and management of private refineries in view of the persistent fuel energy crisis. An attempt is made here at analyzing the prospects and problems of such refineries that are expected to end the fuel energy crisis which started in the 1970s due to increased demand for petroleum products for rehabilitation and reconstruction after the civil war but later metamorphosed into a hydra-headed monster in the 1980s to date. Efforts towards arresting this crisis by the government through the establishment of more refineries, storage depots and network of distribution pipelines etc achieved a short-term solution due to the abysmal low performance of the refineries and facilities in contrast to increasing demand for petroleum products. It is deduced that the low performance resulted from bad and corrupt management by indigenous technocrats and political leaders as well as vandalization of facilities. Prospects for such investments were identified, as well as some of the problems to content with. This is in order to understand the pros and cons of such investments in view of their capital intensiveness and the need to achieve economic goals that must incorporate environmental and social objectives.

KEY WORDS: Fuel Energy, Refinery, Crisis, Prospects, Investment and Market

INTRODUCTION

Obadan (2004) placed Nigeria as the sixth largest member of the Organisation of Oil Exporting Countries (OPEC). The country's total reserve of this very important and strategic resource is put at about 35 billion barrels and the capability for daily production of 3 million barrels per day (Kukpolukun, 2005), actual production is however constrained by OPEC quota allocation to about 2.5 million barrels per day. Tinubu (2004) revealed that the Nigerian petroleum products market requires about 50 million litres of products per day, with PMS accounting for about 20 million litres. Of this, only about 37.5 million litres is made available - a short fall of 25%. Braide (2005), estimated the crisis free demand for petroleum product in Nigeria as 20 million litres for PMS, 12 million litres for AGO and 18 million litres for DPK. Whatever the actual daily consumption figure are, the fact remains that this demand is continuously growing.

The Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), through its down stream sub-sector has however, steadily failed to meet the fuel energy demand of the country, necessitating the review of the country's economic regulations, especially as regards government's participation in the oil and gas industry business with special reference to the down stream sector. This led to its deregulation to pave way for private sector participation in order to induce managerial efficiency and market control of demand and supply at competitive prices.

Scarcity according to Enomoh (2001) started in 1976 and grew into a hydra-headed monster in the 1980s to 1990s following deterioration and gradual break down of existing refineries and the associated distribution chain. Ali-Munguno (2001) opined that the persistent energy supply crisis resulted from gross mismanagement, inefficiency and government's inability to manage the refineries. This complex interplay between demand and supply of petroleum products and their timely supply to the Nigerian consumer is constrained by the following reasons

according to Braide (2005) - Inadequacy of the quantum of crude oil allowed by the federal government for domestic refining; the deficit of available petroleum product needed to satisfy national demand at any given time; the recurrent low capacity utilization of the refineries; epileptic performance of the pipeline distribution network and adverse impact of price regulation in the country.

To understand the seriousness of this problem, it is important to note that the petroleum industry accounts for more than 90 % of the nation's total foreign exchange earnings coupled with its diverse linkages to the other sectors of the economy. It is therefore, necessary that there is continuous uninterrupted supply of the product, most especially the light products –

PMS, AGO & DPK that have direct impact on the lives of the citizenry because of their constant usage in daily production activities. The estimated amount of crude required daily for domestic refining that could satisfy the pent-up demand for petroleum products adequately is put at about 530,000bbl/d, about 85,000bbl/d above the combined refining capacity of the state owned and state run refineries (table 1). This is also some 230,000bbl/d above the quantum allowed by the federal government for domestic refining and consumption.

Table 1. Existing (Government owned) Refineries in Nigeria

Refinery Name	Year established	Capacity
Old Portharcourt Refinery (by SPDC, Nigerianised 1977)	1965	35,000bbl/d
	Later expanded	60,000bbl/d
Warri Ref. and Petrochem. Company (WRPC)	1978	100,000bbl/d
	1986 (Expanded)	125,000bbl/d
Kaduna Ref. and Petrochem. Company (KRPC)	1980	110,000bbl/d
New Portharcourt Refinery	1989	150,000bbl/d
	Total	445,000bbl/d

Though the four refineries have the capacity to meet 80% of domestic demand for products, they have, however, undergone significant depreciation due to old age, neglect and idleness. There is therefore, the need to restore Nigeria from the untold hardship of petroleum products scarcity. For these and other reasons therefore, Nigeria adopted a deregulation policy to liberalize the downstream sector of the oil and gas industry to allow for private sector participation thereby encouraging the establishment of private refineries and avoid the complete degeneration of the fuel energy crisis.

This paper attempts an analysis of the prospects and problems envisaged in the course of trying to make petroleum product readily available for both domestic and foreign markets by such private refineries, considering our investment policies and business ethics coupled with the economic, social, political and cultural environment. This has become necessary in view of the huge capital investment; skilled manpower, sophisticated and automated equipment, safety operations and complex marketing network required by such refineries

Table 2. The Nigerian crude types

Crude type	Specific Gravity / A.P.I	Sulphur content (%)
Forcados	0.8708 / 37	0.2
Bonnylight (sweet)	0.8398 / 37	0.14
Qua – Iboe	0.8398 / 37	0.14
Excravos Blend	0.8448 / 36	0.14
Brass River	0.8063 / 44	0.28

(source; www.nigeriabusinessinfor.com, 2005)

The Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry

The activities of the oil and gas industry world over are categorized into two sub-sectors, the upstream and the down stream. The earlier, comprises activities ranging from the design of business plans, acquisition of acreages, exploration, drilling and production. Crude oil sales also belong to the first category. Refining, storage (depots and tanks), distribution (pipeline network) and products marketing falls within the downstream sub-sector which is synonymous with the oil and gas industry to the citizenry because of its direct impact on their lives. Refinery strategically links petroleum that is almost useless in its crude form and its conversion process (refining) into products of great importance to the daily survival of individuals as well as corporate organizations.

The first successful investment in the Nigerian oil and gas industry was by Shell D'arcy (now SPDC) in 1956 when oil on land was struck at Oloibiri in the present Rivers state, after 18 years of unsuccessful operation (Edmand, 1995). This spurred other oil companies, notably, Agip, Gulf (Chevron), Mobil, Amosea (Texaco), Setrap (Elf), etc to search for oil in the various parts of the Niger Delta region. The establishment of the Nigerian National Oil Company (NNOC) in 1971 and the joining of OPEC by Nigeria, as its 11th member, culminated government's direct involvement in the oil and gas business. Nigeria has an estimated total crude oil reserve in the neighborhood of 35 billion barrels. Government's target is 40 billion barrels by the year 2010 (Kukpolukun 2005). Current daily production however varies due to quota fluctuation as controlled by the world oil and gas demand and supply through OPEC, the global oil Cartel. Nigeria however has the capacity to produce about 3 mbl/d. [www.nigeraoilandgasonline](http://www.nigeraoilandgasonline.com) (2005) revealed that numerous (606) oil fields have been established, located in the swamps of the Niger Delta region. In addition to these, the marginal fields and the deep offshore acreages have become the toast of the day. Table 2, gives the crude oil types and grades that exist in Nigeria while the country's marker crude in the international market are the Bonny light and Forcados. Natural gas reserve is put at about 104t³ feet.

Despite these efforts in the upstream sub-sector, however, the country has to content with a number of recurrent issues that must be addressed in order to sustain such growth, these include, host community and environmental issues; infrastructural development; youth restiveness; technical expertise, etc. The focus here however, is the downstream sector.

Product marketing started in the form of agency representation that was followed by the establishment of branch offices and retail outlets all over the country by the major oil marketing companies - mentioned above (Osibanjo, 1999). By 1960, Shell, Mobil, Texaco, Esso and Total had well established branch offices with adequate storage depots. These depots were largely deregulated with price disparity all over the country and companies operated on healthy competitive basis. Oil produced was refined overseas and imported for sales in the country. Government's involvement began by the construction of the Porthacourt Refinery, commissioned in 1965 with a capacity for 35,000bl/d. This was beginning to satisfy the gasoline requirements of the nation until the internal crisis (civil war) started in 1967. The post-war reconstruction and rehabilitation programme increased the demand for petroleum products and exposed the inability of the major marketers and the NNPC to meet such increased product demand, hence importation that was also limited by storage capacity at the marketers' depots. This is supported by Adigun (1993) who posits that the widespread scarcity that culminated in 1975 resulted from high demand for products after the war for rehabilitation and reconstruction; price equalization all over the country (establishment of Price Equilisation Board) and lack of adequate storage facilities. It became necessary therefore, that the NNPC be rehabilitated and restructured by planning for and the construction of more depots, pipeline network and more refineries to facilitate effective distribution. Local companies and individuals were licensed to market products in order to curb scarcity while prices were fixed by the government of the day. The sequences of refinery establishment that followed and their capacities are contained in table 1. Bridging by trucks was also introduced when the refineries and pipelines started having persistent problems and due to lack of interconnectivity between the four refineries (Abubakar, 2001). The refining, petrochemical and the transportation sub sector of the oil and gas industry still have high government investment but beset by lack of commercial pricing environment and resources to properly manage infrastructure.

Government, through NNPC has found it almost impossible to maintain the four refineries and provide adequate products nation wide. In addition, a large segment of the distribution system is in dear need for maintenance and

upgrade. To therefore ensure self-sufficiency in refining and adequate uninterrupted domestic supply of all petroleum products at reasonable prices and for export, there is need to liberalize the sub-sector for private participation

Need for Private Refineries

The need to remove NNPC's monopoly in refining and distribution of petroleum product in Nigeria has been established. Adubok (2001) revealed that NNPC's performance in this regard has been unimpressive, mainly due to the dual problems of ill-maintained refineries and improper monitoring of products distribution and marketing arising from corrupt management. Alexander oil and gas connection (1998) also observed that, Nigeria, the best African oil producer has in recent years been forced to import refined products due to the inability of the refineries to meet the nation's demand. In its 9th volume 2005, it observed that Nigeria, the 8th largest oil producer in the world with large untapped deposits, has become a curse to the nation's populace as the country today depends largely on importation resulting to ceaseless scarcity, fuel price hikes and attendant effect on prices of other goods and services (Nigeria being a monolithic economy). Finding from www.nigerianbusinessinfor.com (2005) revealed that the break down of refineries and lack of Turn Around Maintenance (TAM) as at when due, between 1966-1988, reduced the total crude processed to 75,000bbl/d or 16% efficiency (comparable to other public enterprises). It is imperative therefore, that such public enterprises be privatized to improve management efficiency in view of the huge financial losses and consistent contributions to fiscal deficit with total liabilities for 39 of such enterprises in excess of #81.1trillion as at December 2000 (El-Rufai, 2005). The importation of petroleum products has become a drain pipe to the economy, though it may look cheap now considering the business environment in Nigeria, it is necessary that petroleum refining is locally carried out in view of its spiraling effect on the other sectors of the economy. Doing so, will drastically reduce product prices that are presently highly manipulated (Aluko, 2003). Such costs arise from high landing cost, demurrage financing, distribution margin, highway maintenance cost, cost of insurance and freight (CI%F), etc. Local refining will reduce these and other costs including importation tax and port charges imposed by and payable to the government.

Prospects

To appraise the investment potentials in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, most especially for the proposed private refineries, it is important to reemphasize that the country is naturally endowed with a lot of mineral resources of economic significance, amongst these is oil and gas. Nigerian oil and gas account for about 80% of the country's total federal revenues, more than 90% of its export earnings and constituting about 30% of the nation's GDP. It also finances all other aspects of the economy. As earlier stated, a total crude reserve of 40billion barrels and daily production rate of 4million bbl/d is targeted by the year 2010. To achieve this, marginal fields and deep offshore acreages are being developed. Tar sands from which crude can be extracted are also known to abound in the country. The Nigerian crude oil is known to be of very good quality, American Petroleum Institute (A.P.I) values ranges between, 25 to 45, sulphur, which reduces the quality of petroleum is also very low in content (table 2). Nigerian oil and gas reserves are also known to be very prolific - found in geologically favorable environment (shallow environment with cheap production cost) as compared to other geologically complex areas. This will continue to attract long-term investment in the sector. Crude availability, which is a major investment factor for the proposed private refineries is guaranteed over a long period of time. This is coupled with the high product demand both locally and internationally which is not being met by the existing refineries. Nigeria's large population - presently put at about 140million and an annual growth rate of about 2.3% as announced by the Nigerian Population Commission (2007), can economically sustain the establishment of numerous private refineries. More so, the country is known to be strategically located for the oil and gas international trade, sea and land routes exist to service both the local and international markets, especially the African sub region where large products demand exist.

Storage, distribution and marketing facilities belonging to both the federal government and major marketers exist, however, at different functional stages. The NNPC is known to have numerous depots scattered all over the country, 11,000km of pipeline network, two jetties, one export terminal, a single point mooring buoy, etc. These facilities are essential for the convenient and effective operations of the private refineries without which the products, even when refined cannot reach the consumers. The efficiency and convenience of these facilities need to be ascertained, when proved adequate, it shall go a long way to reducing their initial capital investment

cost of making products available to end-users. Products can also be moved through bridging by trucks and / or the rail, if and when rehabilitated. Refineries may either directly dispense their products by establishing retail outlets or by the utilization of existing ones belonging to the major and independent marketers that control the dispensing outlets.

www.nigerianoilandgasonline (2005), observed that in addition to the above, the following incentives also exist for the private refineries, the federal government's encouragement of foreign investors in the oil and gas industry; a five-year tax holiday (exemption) for all new plants from start of production; foreign investors can now own 100% equity share in any venture incorporated in the country; guaranteed export earning- earnings from the export of any local production is permitted to be retained in an approved export account in any country of choice nominated by the investor and a lot more

Envisaged Problems

The liberalization of the downstream sector of the oil and gas industry to allow for private participation has been accepted as the only solution to the fuel scarcity problem because no option has been preferred in its place (Enomoh, 2001). However, the private refineries must operate, balancing government's interest and management interest, surviving the turbulent investment climate in the country and thereby solving the perennial fuel scarcity problem. Though no private refinery is yet operational in the country, this study however reveals that the following problems are envisaged and must be considered despite the prospects and incentives mentioned above. These include amongst other things the following: unstable policies and government procedures; complex technology requirement and expertise to establish and manage refineries; high capital requirement; the unwillingness on the part of marketers to change from the status quo that greatly benefits them and the abysmal low level of infrastructural development. These will definitely add to the total operational costs that will eventually be paid for by the consumers and hence ending up not addressing the price issue, etc. This 'climate' according to Tinubu (2004), will not allow foreign investors in the oil sector. Business is undertaken in very unconventional way in Nigeria, all known international laws of doing such has been torn to shreds thereby allowing investors to exploit and extort the consumers who are hardly protected by the policy implementers and the law enforcement agents (Soeze, 2005). Instability in policies and the haphazard nature of their implementation constitute great problems. With this situation, investors face high risks of success. There is therefore the need for remediation of this problem, most especially, policy reviews and implementation as regards international business. Another major problem that might confront the private refineries and militate against stable products price, is the continuous fluctuation in the international market prices of crude oil coupled with the fact that strategic reserves that will guarantee availability for a long time and thereby absorb short-term price increases are lacking. Local sourcing of technology and human inputs are also lacking, more so, sourcing them overseas implies repatriation of revenue with very little positive impact on the domestic economy. The enforcement of local content policy must be encouraged to train Nigerians in refinery operation and management. It is also identified that though, it is easier and convenient to move products by pipelines, the safety of such pipelines network in Nigeria is presently not guaranteed. Its monitoring and surveillance is weak and cases of sabotage through vandalization abounds. To curb this menace, investors must be willing to strive for sustainability rather than profit maximization through community partnering and youth empowerment. In addition, competent monitoring and surveillance teams should be established to ensure safety of such facilities that have become target of the aggrieved. Security agents should institute rapid response initiatives in the pipeline areas, putting in place technical devices that, alerts a command and control center as in other oil producing countries. Other problems that would be encountered by such refineries are high interest rates, unstable exchange rate, inflation and bureaucracy, etc

CONCLUSION

The failure of the existing state owned refineries to meet the Nigerian petroleum products demand has given credence to the liberalization of the downstream sector of the oil and gas industry and thereby encouraging the establishment of private refineries. It is believed that such private refineries' operation would be a lucrative investment that will lead to satisfying domestic as well as external demand for petroleum products at appropriate and affordable prices, earn foreign exchange, eliminate import and thereby reducing cost and also improving on local capacity utilization. The petrochemical units of the refineries are particularly figured out as potential source

of massive employment to Nigerians, this is due to the numerous small-scale industries that can emerge using their by-products as raw materials. They are therefore encouraged. Great prospects exist for such refineries in view of the country's high and fast growing population and large and different grades of hydrocarbon reserves that can sustain such investments for along time exist (40 billion barrels reserve is being targeted by the year 2010). More so, advances in technology for alternative energy sources are low. Nigeria is also strategically located and can be accessed by neighboring African countries for petroleum products, product market is therefore guaranteed. Despite these prospects, however, certain problems exist that may still hinder the smooth take off and operations of these refineries, Nigerians neither possess the expertise nor the local capacity to fully accommodate such ventures. The success of the refineries is much dependent on the activities of the multinational who possess the requisite expertise (Avuru 2004, Ewuga 2004 and Olaleye 2004). They are however skeptical and unenthusiastic embarking on this investments in view of the complexities of doing business in the country. Care, must therefore, be taken to avoid this heavy dependence on foreign market for inputs – expertise, parts and machinery as well as routine maintenance services due to the dearth of local technology and infrastructure. Approval for refinery licenses must incorporate the local content policy for the continuous involvement and training of local indigenous operators because sole reliance on foreign investors might be a risky decision. They are likely to pull out at the slightest unfavorable business conditions. This may however not apply to Multinationals with businesses in the upstream sector of the Nigerian oil and gas industry, they should be enticed if not mandated to individually or jointly set up refineries and process part of their crude allocation locally as recommended by Adebok (2001) and presently being supported by the National Assembly. These oil companies have huge investment interest in the upstream to protect and not likely to leave in a hurry. More so, their resources availability and managerial efficiency will be brought to bear in the management of such refineries.

It is also identified that the government on the one hand must show political will to transform the Niger Delta. Violence and other community related problems this could be achieved by fully involving the people of the area in making policies that affects them and participate in resource allocation (Nwosu, 2004). While Investors on the other hand must be transparent in all their activities to reduce anxiety and suspense that have woven the Nigeria oil and gas industry into a cult (Avuru, 2004). Considering all the above therefore, it is necessary that intending investors critically analyze all plans and steps necessary for the establishment of private refineries and the production of different petroleum by-products at maximum benefit. Such plans must accommodate changes in consumption pattern, crude supply, political risks, growing energy conservation policies, future market prices and the continuous search for alternative energy sources. Refineries once built has very little possibility for adaptation, flexibility for those on the drawing board is however, infinite.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, A. (2001), How to end fuel shortage by ex-PPMC Boss, edited by Nwora, C; "Guardian" Newspaper, 3/06/01, pp1-2
- Adigun, B.A. (1993): Averting oil shortage in Nigeria – The efficiency and adequacy of supply and distribution facilities in Nigeria, Energy policy agenda, Lagos. Edited By Fawibe, O., pp197
- Adebok, A.S-Z. (2001): An appraisal of deregulation as a strategic policy to end Nigeria's Fuel Energy Crisis, M.B.A (mgt) project, Imo State University, unpublished, pp 47-55
- Alexander Oil and Gas Connection (1988), vol.3, pp 1-3
- Alexander Oil and Gas Connection (2005), Ogel's special study, vol.4, ed. Othman and Bunter, pp1
- Ali-monguno, S. (2001): Fuel deregulation: a symphony of discord Guardian Features, 20/02/01
- Aluko, M.E. (2003): On the fuel price hike and why we are where we are, view point in Lagosforum.com, 2/3/03, pp1-16

Avuru, A. (2004): Ensuring Transparency in Nigerian oil industry, Thisday Perspective, 17/03/04, Pp26

Braide, A.M. (2005): The mechanics and dynamics of fuel scarcity in Nigeria part 1, www.onelga.com, 19/01/2005, pp1-5

Edmand, W.D. (1995): Promoting Investment in Nigerian upstream oil and gas resources, Keynote address, Re-channelling Nigeria's Energy Resources for Economic Revival, Ed. Fawibe, O. International Energy Forum, pp 43-54

El-Rufai, N.A (2005): Why Nigerian refineries can't be sold, ed. Othman and Bunter, in Alexander Oil and Gas, vol. 9, no. 6, pp1-9

Enomoh, G. (2001): Deregulate the entire petroleum sector not just price alone, Guardian Executive brief, 5/3/01, pp46

Ewuga, S. (2004) Our Business attitude, Thisday Perspective, 09/05/04, pg18

Kukpolukun, F. (2005): NNPC's silent revolution, Tell Magazine Special Edition, no.8, 21/02/05 Pp1-10

Nigerian Population Commission (NPC) - Population census results released 2007

Nwosu, G.F. (2004): NDDC and the burden of developing the Niger Delta, the Guardian Forum, Ed. Aderinbibe Y. pp15

Obadan, M. (2004): the Nigerian business environment, Thisday Newspaper, 14/06/04

Olaleye, Y. (2004): Fuel price hike will discourage foreign investment inflow. Thisday business World, Thisday Newspaper, 9/3/04

Osibanjo, O (1999): Petroleum products distribution and marketing and the scarcity problem M.Sc Thesis in energy and petroleum economics, Delta state university, Unpublished

Soeze, C. (2005): Deregulation of the downstream sector of the Nigerian economy, Vanguard Newspaper, 15/02/05

Tinubu, W. (2004): Highly Inflammable – 1, Verdict according to Olusegun Adeniyi, thisday Newspaper, 10/06/04, pp64

www.nigeriaoilandgasonline (2005), The Nigerian Crude Oil Types and Quality, 19/01/05

www.nigerianbusinessinfor.com (2005), The Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry, 19/01/05

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